

Oxidative deamination and decarboxylation of L-isomers of amino acids by potassium permanganate in moderately concentrated sulphuric acid medium

B. R. Sahu^a, Vijay R. Chourey^{*b}, Shakuntala Pandey^c, L. V. Shastry^c and V. R. Shastry^c

^aC. M. D. College, Bilaspur, India

^bGovernment Autonomous P. G. College, Dhar-454 001, India

^cSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, India

Manuscript received 22 December 1997, revised 8 October 1998, accepted 15 October 1998

The oxidation reactions of L-isomers of amino acids, viz. asparagic acid, glutamic acid, asparagine and glutamine have been carried out in moderately concentrated sulphuric acid medium. The reactions are found to be two-stage processes. In both the stages the reactions follow first order behaviour with respect to each of substrate and permanganate. The reactions are acid-catalysed and the rate is related to the activity of water and also to the acidity function. Primary salt-effect is nil, but at higher concentration of neutral salts the logarithm of the rate constant is linearly related to ionic strength. Specific ionic effects have also been investigated. Activation parameters have been reported. Mechanism pertinent with the observation has been suggested.

The study on the kinetics of oxidation of amino acids has received considerable interest¹. However, much less attention has been given to the L-isomers of amino acids. Hence investigations have been carried out on L-isomers and results are reported here.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that the oxidation of L-asparagic acid, L-glutamic acid, L-asparagine and L-glutamine is a

double-stage process and both the stages are linear, indicating unit order with respect to permanganate. This was confirmed by varying initial concentration of permanganate which did not show any change in the pseudo-first order rate constants k_1 (for the first stage) and k'_1 (for second stage). In case of L-asparagic acid, first stage follows second slow stage, while in other three amino acids, first stage follows second fast stage (Fig. 1).

The rate constants are found to increase with increasing concentration of amino acids. Plots of $\log k_1$ (and $\log k'_1$) against \log [amino acids] give straight lines with almost unit slope in each case. The plots of $1/k_1$ (and $1/k'_1$) against $1/[\text{amino acids}]$ (Fig. 2) give straight lines passing through the origin. This confirms first order with respect to substrates and suggests that no intermediate complex is formed between the substrate and permanganate². However, if any complex is formed its formation constant would be extremely small³.

Reaction velocities of both the stages get enhanced with the $[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 1). Hence, HMnO_4 is the active oxidizing species, supported by the spectral studies⁴. Rate of oxidation is strictly proportional to the concentration of the substrate and it indicates that HMnO_4 oxidizes the substrate directly⁵. The two Zucker-Hammett⁶ plots were found linear. This shows that the reactions are acid-catalyzed. However, none of the plots produced the ideal slope value of unity (Table 2). In view of these departure from ideal slope values, the hypotheses of Bunnett⁷ and Bunnett-Olsen⁸ were tested. The slope values indicate that the water molecule should act as a proton-abstracting agent in the rate-determining step⁷. The values of $-H_0$ and $\log {}^a\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been taken from Paul and Long⁹ and Bunnett⁷ respectively.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time: (1) [L-asparagine] = 0.08 M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 4.0 M, (2) [L-glutamine] = 0.02 M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 3.0 M, (3) L-glutamic acid] = 0.024 M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 5.0 M, (4) [L-asparagic acid] = 0.02 M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = 4.0 M; temp = 313 K, $[\text{KMnO}_4]$ = 8.88×10^{-4} M.

Table 1. Variation of sulphuric acid concentration

$KMnO_4 = 8.8 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp. = 313 K
 $[H_2SO_4] -H_0 \quad -\log {}^aH_2O$

M			L-Asparatic acid (0.02M)		L-Glutamic acid (0.02M)		L-Asparagine (0.08M)		L-Glutamine (0.02M)	
			I-Stage (Fast)	II-Stage (Slow)	I-Stage (Slow)	II-Stage (Fast)	I-Stage (Slow)	II-Stage (Fast)	I-Stage (Slow)	II-Stage (Fast)
3.5	1.62	0.111	2.930	2.361	1.568	2.720	1.120	4.601	5.162	18.700
4.0	1.85	0.142	3.750	2.955	2.111	3.704	1.482	5.313	6.840	21.510
4.5	2.06	0.176	5.202	3.681	2.832	4.843	1.920	6.002	9.152	24.520
5.0	2.28	0.219	6.481	4.312	3.640	6.360	2.833	6.776	12.04	27.250
5.5	2.51	0.267	8.423	5.132	4.701	8.103	3.691	7.500	15.10	29.610
6.0	2.76	0.320	11.310	6.883	5.961	8.921	5.222	8.409	-	-

I-stage : $k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. II-stage : $k_1' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$.

Table 2. Correlation of rate with acid concentration

Correlation	Parameter	L-Asparatic acid		L-Glutamic acid		L-Asparagine		L-Glutamine	
		I-Stage	II-Stage	I-Stage	II-Stage	I-Stage	II-Stage	I-Stage	II-Stage
(A) Zucker-Hammett plots :									
(1) H_0 against $\log k$	-	0.50	0.40	0.58	0.56	0.59	0.25	0.59	0.30
(2) $\log [\text{Acid}]$ against $\log k$	-	2.80	1.71	2.40	2.20	2.77	1.25	2.35	1.15
(B) Bunnett plot :									
$\log k - \log [\text{Acid}]$ against $\log {}^aH_2O$	w*	1.78	1.05	1.82	1.73	2.08	0.12	2.01	Absent
(C) Bunnett-Olsen plot (LFER) :									
$\log k + H_0$ against $H_0 + \log [\text{Acid}]$	ϕ	0.75	0.64	0.63	0.66	0.64	0.92	0.65	0.95

The specific rate increases with the rise in temperature. The reactions were studied at 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/k_1$ (and $1/k_1'$) vs $1/[\text{amino acid}]$: (1) L-asparagine, (2) L-glutamic acid, (3) L-glutamine, (4) L-asparatic acid; temp. = 313 K, $[KMnO_4] = 8.88 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 5.0 M$ (3.0 M for L-glutamine).

to evaluate various kinetic and activation parameters. It was observed that oxidation reactions follow the Arrhenius relationship. The results are summarized in Table 3.

No primary salt-effect was observed by adding neutral salts within the concentration limits demanded for the applicability of Bronstead-Bjerrum equation, but at higher concentrations of added neutral salts, logarithm of the rate constant is linearly related to the ionic strength in accordance with equation¹⁰, $\log k_{obs} = \log k_0 \mu + B$

In order to investigate the specific effect of cations and anions on the reaction velocity, sodium salts of anions and sulphates of cations were taken at their identical molar concentrations. It was observed that both anions and cations do exerts their specific effects on the reaction velocity. The order of the effectiveness of the anions in all the four cases of oxidation of these amino acids is, $ClO_4^- > HSO_4^- > SO_4^{2-}$; while the series for the order of the effectiveness of cations are (i) in case of L-asparatic acid, $Zn^{2+} > Mg^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$, (ii) in case of L-glutamic acid, $Zn^{2+} > Mg^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > K^+ > Li^+ > Na^+$, (iii) in the case of L-asparagine, $Zn^{2+} > Mg^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > K^+ > Na^+$ and (iv) in the case of L-glutamine, $Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > K^+ > Na^+$.

Under the conditions employed, the products of the reaction were identified as ammonia, CO_2 and the corresponding aldehydes. The aldehyde was confirmed by preparing 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives of oxidation products from etheral extracts. Their melting points

Table 3. Kinetic and activation parameters

Amino acid	Temp. Coeff. (303–313 K)	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	PZ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
L-Asparatic acid (0.02 M)					
I-Stage	1.86	49.15	45.22	6.05×10^5	-134.86
II-Stage	2.08	57.95	55.48	2.04×10^7	-105.60
L-Glutamic acid (0.024 M)					
I-Stage	1.77	47.31	44.97	3.08×10^5	-140.55
II-Stage	2.28	65.40	58.50	9.59×10^7	-92.70
L-Asparagine (0.08 M)					
I-Stage	2.12	63.55	60.10	1.69×10^8	-87.97
II-Stage	2.26	64.65	62.35	4.47×10^8	-79.88
L-Glutamine (0.02 M)					
I-Stage	2.79	83.78	80.15	3.13×10^{11}	-25.28
II-Stage	2.97	86.12	83.00	1.07×10^{13}	+4.17

compared with the reference compounds reported by others¹¹. The presence of free radicals as intermediates was confirmed by the reduction of mercuric chloride¹².

Stoichiometric study was carried out by keeping the concentrations of the substrate and permanganate in the ratio 1 : 0.8 moles. It was found that substrate and oxidant reacts in the ratio of 5 : 2 moles. The overall reaction may be written as

The values of entropy of activation for all these reactions are less and negative, indicating that both first and second stage processes come under the category of slow reactions¹³. It also suggests a bimolecular reaction in rate-determining step in presence of water, acting as a proton-abstracting agent in acid-catalysed reactions¹⁴. The positive salt-effect further indicates that the reaction is between a positive ion and a molecule¹⁵ in the rate-determining step.

On the basis of the kinetic results and other evidences the following scheme of mechanism is proposed for the first stage process only. At such a high acid concentration the COOH groups in all the four amino acids and the amide groups in L-asparagine and L-glutamine are highly 'O' and 'N' protonated¹⁶ respectively.

where, R is CH₂COOH for L-asparatic acid, CH₂CONH₂ for L-asparagine, CH₂CH₂CONH₂ for L-glutamine, and CH₂CH₂COOH for L-glutamic acid.

The above mechanism leads us to give the rate expression as

$$-\frac{d[MnO_4^-]}{dt} = K [Amino\ acid] [MnO_4^-] \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where, } K = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^3}{1 + K_3 [H^+]} \quad (11)$$

The order of reactivity has been observed as, L-glutamine > L-asparatic acid > L-glutamic acid > L-asparagine.

Details regarding occurrence of the two stages can not be furnished at present; it might be suggested that these stages are probably due to creation of optimum concentration of some intermediate product or due to autocatalysis¹⁷.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Potassium permanganate solution was prepared. Double-distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. Progress of the reactions was followed by iodometric estimations of the reaction mixture. Kinetic experiments were carried out in a UK-10 thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Research Fellowship to one of them (B.R.S.).

References

1. Z. Kovates, *Magyar Kim Folyirat (Hung.)*, 1960, **66**, 181; K. B. Reddy, B. Sethuram and T. N. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 391; G. Chandra and S. N. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 773; R. Boominathan and P. S. M. Kannan, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1995, **11**, 49.
2. R. N. Mehrotra, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 1123.
3. P. S. Sankhla and R. N. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 1077, 1081.
4. R. Stewart in "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", ed. K. B. Wiberg, Academic, New York, 1965, Part A, p. 48.
5. G. V. Bakore, R. Dayal and P. Nath, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1964, **19**, 227.
6. L. Zucker and L. P. Hammett, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2791.
7. J. F. Bunnett *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4956, 4968.
8. J. F. Bunnett and F. P. Olsen, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 1899, 1917.
9. M. A. Paul and F. A. Long, *Chem. Rev.*, 1957, **51**, 1.
10. A. A. Frost and R. G. Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley, New York, 1965, p.151.
11. M. Bhargav, B. Sethuram and T. N. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 770; R. G. R. Bacon, W. J. W. Hann and D. Steward, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1966, 1388.
12. A. Y. Drummond and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2836, 3119.
13. S. Glasstone, "Recent Advances in General Chemistry", Chrch Hill, London, 1936, p. 317.
14. W. R. Jenck, "Catalysis in Chemistry and Enzymology", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1969, p. 608.
15. A. K. Wadhawan, P. S. Sankhala and R. N. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 567.
16. M. Liler, "Reaction Mechanism in Sulphuric Acid", Academic, London, 1971, p.104.
17. L. S. Levitt and F. R. Melinovski, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4517.